

KT/V - TEST DIAGNOSIS IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY

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When a patient begins dialysis treatment, whether it is hemodialysis or peritoneal dialysis (PD), they begin to feel better as the blood begins to clear. To make sure that you are receiving adequate dialysis, you need to schedule a laboratory test to check how well dialysis works on the patient. The members of the Urea Union (URR) are like-minded due to the fact that they have united, so, whatever it is, they are splitting up. If the patient undergoes hemodialysis three times a week, each course of treatment should reduce the level of urea (also called AMC or urea nitrogen in the blood) at least 65 percent.

The aim is to study an indicator for calculating how much creatinine and urea has been purified in the blood of a patient on dialysis.

Research methods.

Ct/V, as before, are a large business audience.

- K = clearance — the amount of urea that can become a dilizer (liters/minute).
- t = time – duration of treatment (minutes)
- V = volume — number of people in the body (liters).

For hemodialysis, recommendations to the Doctor were prescribed three times a week (initiation according to the quality of the results of those holding a senior position). the main value, Ct/V is not less than 1,2.

For continuous outpatient peritoneal dialysis (PAPD), the guidelines recommend a weekly IV CT value of at least 2.0, taking into account any remaining kidney function during PAPD treatment. To begin with, we strive to ensure that everything is done as efficiently as possible, so that you produce within just 24 hours. URR and Kt/V tests. These laboratory tests are performed monthly. Ct scan first/In general, it is produced quarterly. Ask your dialysis nurse every time what your values are. If your values do not reach adequate figures, contact your doctor to increase the dose of dialysis.

Results. During hemodialysis, the blood pump is set to a constant speed to push blood through the dialyzer back into the body. Your doctor prescribes the blood flow rate. This is usually from 300 to 500 ml/min (milliliters per minute). Ask your technician to show you how to determine the blood flow rate on your machine. When using many dialyzers, a blood flow rate of more than 400 ml/min can increase the removal of toxins. The speed of blood flow is limited by the size of the access, tubes and needles. The hemodialysis machine monitors the pressure of your blood inside the tubes and the dialyzer. Depending on the device, blood pressure is measured in one of two places. One of them is between your access and the blood pump (blood pressure in front of the pump). The other is located between the blood pump and the dialyzer (blood pressure after the pump). The hemodialysis machine measures the venous pressure between the dialyzer and the access point. If your venous pressure rises from week to week, it may mean a narrowing of the blood vessels in your access. Caught early, it can be fixed.

Conclusion. To improve the washing of peripheral tissues, provide physical activity to muscles and good blood flow. In the process of improving the treatment plan, the task is to minimize complications and improve the quality of life of patients on hemodialysis. In order to achieve the effectiveness of procedures, first of all it is necessary to pay attention to the patient's state of health in order to make therapy as comfortable as possible.

References:

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